

Rethinking Alternative Dispute Resolution in Conflict Resolution and Nation-Building in Nigeria

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Abstract

The inadequacy of litigation in addressing the menace of conflict, which led to growing dissatisfaction with the system, coupled with a favourable political climate that sought alternative means of resolving disputes outside litigation, led to the resurgence of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) across the globe. This study interrogated the significance of ADR in conflict resolution and nation-building, focusing on its influence in achieving reconciliation and peace in the Nigeria. The study adopted a quantitative research approach, relying on both primary and secondary methods of data collection and analysis. 200 copies of questionnaire were administered to respondents, out of which 160 were retrieved. Analysis was carried out using inferential statistical tools in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 19) at a 0.05 level of significance. The study found that ADR offers several advantages, including cost-effectiveness, decongestion of courts, the promotion of social justice, and the provision of platforms for the amicable settlement of disputes that often produce win-win outcomes and reconciliation. Despite these benefits, its development is constrained by factors such as the absence of binding precedent, difficulties in balancing power relations between disputing parties, limited public sanction, and a shortage of skilled practitioners compounded by inadequate training. The study concludes that ADR is closely linked to reconciliation and peace, both of which are essential for nation-building. It therefore recommends sustained public enlightenment, improved planning and information management, the engagement of qualified personnel with adequate training, and increased funding for both public and private ADR centres.

Keywords: Alternative Dispute Resolution, Conflict, Conflict Resolution, Court System, Litigation, Nation-Building, Reconciliation, Peace

Introduction

Peace is one of the most treasured and supreme human needs in the history of humankind. The search for peace has become the preference of humans which is a persistent and interminable task, but unfortunately, it has been consistently and tragically marred at critical junction by conflict. Conflict has therefore become a factor to reckon with in the affairs of men. In addition to taking lives, destroying communities, and undermining progress toward development, conflicts often leave a legacy of pain, dread, and animosity. Countries are likely to return to violence in the absence of efficient, inclusive peace and reconciliation mechanisms (United States of America International Development, 2011). The inevitability and the prevalence of conflicts call for radical approach for people to live a peaceful life devoid of fear and danger. The need for conflict resolution and the method chosen is crucial and imperative as two people cannot see a specific situation precisely the same way. Desmond Tutu commented “without forgiveness and reconciliation, there is no future” (Tutu, 1999). This affirmation emphasizes the universal desire for reconciliation and peace.

In managing incessant conflict that ravage the entire world system, a fair trial "within a reasonable time by a court or other tribunal established by law and constituted in such manner as to secure its independence and impartiality" is guaranteed by the constitutions of several nations that complement the universal declaration of peace. In essence court became an official means of managing conflict across the globe. Despite this impressive provision of access to justice across the globe through litigation, Nigeria inclusive, court system has suffered setback which has severally escalated conflict. This led to growing discontentment of the populace with the litigation process due to its rigid technicalities, prohibitive cost, delay in justice administration, congestion, and mono-track nature to mention a few (Onyema, 2013). The growing discontentment with the litigation process and the favourable political climate seeking alternative means of resolving conflict aside litigation consequently resurrect Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) across the world at a time Frank Sander (Professor of Law at Harvard University) developed the concept of multi-door courthouse which is a collection of alternative systems of dispute resolution in the United States of America (Oddiri, 2004).

In the past, non-judicial indigenous techniques of resolving disputes have been utilised by communities throughout the world, including Africa. Its widespread promotion and spread, as well as its growing application as a mean to achieve objectives outside the resolution of particular conflicts, are what make it innovative. The Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) movement began in the 1970s in the United States of America as a social movement to use mediation to settle civil rights conflicts that affected the entire community. It also aimed to reduce the high expense and length of litigation that resulted from an overcrowded court system (Adedeji, 2021a). In the 1980s, a search for more effective and efficient alternatives to litigation led to an increase in demand for Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in the business sector (Goldberg et al., 1992). Globally, both developed and developing nations have seen a surge in the ADR movement. This has been replicated in Nigeria by the establishment of the Lagos Citizens' Mediation Bureau (CMB) formerly Citizens' Mediation Centre (CMC) and Lagos Multi-Door Courthouse in 1999 and 2002 respectively as the first of their kind in Africa. The much greater benefits derived from the established is the reduction of parties' expenses, time and efficiency.

Since then, the number of private and public corporation providing ADR services has increased rapidly along with the usage of both public and private ADR (arbitration and mediation) in commercial settings. Current legislation permits and promotes the use of negotiation and other types of Alternative Dispute Resolution by agencies in rule-making, public consultation, and administrative conflict settlement. Due to the delays in litigation, business partners, investors, and

attorneys are more aware of the benefits of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) processes. ADR clauses are present in the majority of contracts nowadays. Contemporarily, the courts send disputing parties to the public ADR centres to try to resolve their differences through one of the available ADR options. The Arbitration and Conciliation Act is being adopted and modified by many nations across the Africa which has led to tremendous increase and rise in the activities of public and private ADR (Ekpenyong, 2014). The administration of justice in Africa, particularly in Nigeria, needs significant adjustments to meet the demands of the 21st century advancements, which made Alternative Dispute Resolution a necessary model. Therefore, the study is designed to interrogate the influence of Alternative Dispute Resolution in conflict resolution and nation-building focusing on its impact in achieving reconciliation and peace in Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study was to interrogate the significance of Alternative Dispute Resolution in conflict resolution and nation-building, while the specific objectives were:

- 1) To analyse the impact of Alternative Dispute Resolution in achieving reconciliation and peace in contemporary Nigeria.
- 2) To examine the relationship between Alternative Dispute Resolution and the modern-day conflict resolution in nation-building.

Research Questions

1. What are the impacts of Alternative Dispute Resolution in achieving reconciliation and peace in contemporary Nigeria?
2. Is there any relationship between ADR and modern-day conflict resolution in nation-building?

Literature Review

One of humanity's greatest ideals has always been peace. It is perceived as concord, or peace and harmony. According to Rummel (1981), it can be described as a state of justice or a balance or equilibrium of powers. Peace may also be termed antagonistic conflict, violence, or war. Peace can be broad, encompassing an entire society (global peace), or restricted, referring to certain relationships in a given circumstance (peace treaty). Peace means freedom from war and violence, particularly when individuals coexist peacefully and without conflict. The typical, non-conflicting state of a country, a collection of nations, or the entire planet is peace. Peace is an agreement or pact to put a stop to hostilities and refrain from future combat between warring or antagonistic nations, groups, etc. It is a condition of harmony between individuals or organizations, particularly in interpersonal relationships.

Reconciliation is defined by Kriesberg (1998) as the process of creating a mutually agreeable agreement between antagonistic or previously adversarial individuals or groups. Restoring harmony and cooperation amongst adversaries who have caused harm in a reciprocal or one-sided manner is the goal of reconciliation (Fisher, 1999). Reconciliation is frequently used to describe a somewhat cordial relationship in which severe harm is inflicted on both parties. In order to develop new views and a new shared experience, it must be proactive in attempting to establish an

encounter where individuals may concentrate on their relationship and share their thoughts, feelings, and experiences with one another (Lederach, 1997).

Conflict which is in contrast with the concept of peace and reconciliation is an occurrence that is inherent in every society. It is more than a mere disagreement. It can be characterised as a circumstance where individuals feel that their well-being is in danger (physical, emotional, power, status, etc.). People in conflict therefore use their values, culture, beliefs, knowledge, experience, gender, and other factors to filter their perceptions and responses. In the workplace, conflicts are also considered common. Conflict to a large extent is a degree of foreseeable circumstances that obviously arises as we go about managing multifaceted and day to day routine (Adedeji, 2021a). The impact of conflicts on human development has led to the realisation of the need to prioritise the resolution of conflict and to promote a culture of peace.

Disagreements between parties are typically the cause of disputes in the realm of human relationships and business transactions. The urge to settle these conflicts as soon as possible frequently develops, and litigation in court with clear-cut win/lose results is a popular strategy employed by disputants (Spencer, 2002). In Nigeria and even globally, litigation is currently the most popular and well-established method of resolving disputes. The court system has been replaced by the other systems, which now play supporting functions. As a result, the idea of ADR encompasses a broad range of procedures that can be tailored to the particular requirements of parties in settling disagreements or conflicts; each procedure provides an alternative to litigation. Whether they are used to manage community tensions, landlord-tenant disputes, or multi-million Naira disputes, these procedures can be used alone or in conjunction with others, but they all have the fundamental feature of bringing disputants together through an unbiased third party and mutually agreeing on the terms of settlement (Spencer, 2002). Study on the consistent growth of ADR in Nigeria has revealed that the method of litigation is time consuming, expensive and not easily managed due to substantial numerical increase of cases across the courts which have manifested in congestion and delay of justice. Hence, the focus has been placed on ADR as a means of resolving disputes due to the limitation of litigation.

Even though alternative dispute resolution dates back hundreds of years, people have been negotiating and resolving conflicts both formally and informally before historical journals documented human efforts in this area. Since the political and civil unrest of the 1960s, it has expanded quickly in the United States. ADR is seen as a process for resolving conflicts without the formal litigation route. ADR is a phrase commonly used to describe an informal dispute resolution procedure when the parties meet with an impartial third-party who assists them in resolving their disagreement in a manner that is less formal and frequently more consensual than what is done in court (Spangler, 2003 referenced in Adedeji, 2022). It is a mechanism in which matters are resolved between two warring parties in a conducive environment devoid of strict legal technicalities by an umpire.

ADR also refers to the collection of methods communities use to settle conflicts without going through expensive adversarial litigation. According to Adedeji (2022), it is a broad range of dispute resolution procedures that serve as alternatives to extensive legal proceedings. It is also regarded as those methods that are employed to settle conflicts more quickly and fairly without ruining existing relationships. The phrase may be used to describe a facilitated settlement in which parties are urged to engage in direct negotiations with each other instead of engaging in legal contestation. It is an endeavour to reach judgments that are acceptable to both sides, which entails the use of techniques, protocols, and abilities intended to produce an agreement that is fulfilling and acceptable to all parties (Aina, 2005). However, mediation, arbitration and conciliation are the

most popular types of alternative dispute resolution. Additional methods include fact-finding, conferences, judicial settlement, ombudsmen, special inquiries, etc.

In contrast to the processes of pursuing justice, fairness, or even redress in a legal court, Alternative Dispute Resolution serves a more conciliatory role and provides a speedier and less expensive platform for settling disagreements. The ADR process is adaptable, encourages and safeguards parties' privacy, and fosters a relaxed and cordial environment where parties can converse in an effort to come to an acceptable agreement which is the cornerstone of peace (Adedeji and Adimula, 2025). ADR models can simply be imports of United States procedures or hybrid experiments that combine aspects of traditional dispute resolution with ADR models. ADR procedures are being used to achieve a variety of political, business, legal, and social objectives. Many nations increasingly use alternative dispute resolution procedures due to the demands of commercial transactions.

The concept of nation-building can mean different things to different people. The most recent conceptualisation conceives nation-building as approach of aiding dysfunctional, unstable, or failed states or economies to develop civil society, government infrastructure, dispute resolution procedures, and economic sustenance in order to enhance the stability of the affected nation. Nation-building is important because security requires a strong state, creating an integrated national community is crucial to creating a state, and creating an integrated national community may have social and economic prerequisites or co-requisites (Stephenson, 2005). Professor Frank Sander advocated for an all-inclusive justice centre where all court cases would be screened by a clerk to determine the best medium for their resolution, which could either be litigation, arbitration, mediation, or another method, in order to lessen frustration with the administration of justice (Sander, 1976).

In addition to offering litigation as a means of settling disputes, the modern court house has evolved into a comprehensive dispute centre that offers disputants access to additional procedures or channels. The other options could be arbitration, conciliation, mediation, negotiation, etc. The best method for settling disputes can be determined by a number of factors, including the nature of the disagreement, the relationship between disputants, and the amount in dispute. Prof Sander envisioned a multi-door, multifaceted dispute resolution centre within the court's administrative structure, with doors open to a wide range of dispute resolution procedures. This idea was tested in the US, and its success prompted the construction of multi-door court houses in numerous nations, including Nigeria. According to Osinbajo (2005), the Lagos High Court has over 40,000 pending cases as at May 2002. There was little prospect that many of the cases would be resolved in ten years. The Lagos multi-door court house (LMDC) was founded in 2002 as a Public-Private Partnership Initiative (PPPI) by the Negotiation and Conflict Management Group (NCMG), a non-governmental organisation that supports the legal system, and the High Court of Justice of Lagos State.

For the first time, Nigeria's constitution provides constitutional support for arbitration and other types of Alternative Dispute Resolution as a conflict resolution process. According to Oddiri (2004), section 19(d) of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 Constitution specifically allows for the resolution of conflicts by arbitration, mediation, conciliation, negotiation, and adjudication. The importance of arbitration and other kinds of ADR in resolving a variety of conflicts has constitutional backing. In addition to the judicial powers granted to the courts by the

constitution, arbitration and other forms of Alternative Dispute Resolution have a constitutional status (Mitchard, 1997). The goal of ADR centres is to encourage social fairness and fair play among individual citizens in a non-legal way. The great advantage of the ADR centre is that it provides an informal and friendly resolution of conflict for people at free of charge or at reduced rate (Oluyede, 1994). Though often voluntary, ADR is sometimes instructed by the courts, which require that disputant try mediation before they take their case to court. On this note, ADR guarantee an opportunity for parties to exploits more means of resolution if the outcome of the process is not satisfactory.

Despite various scholarly studies into conflict resolution, most of them have focused on the root causes of conflict, its implications, resolution through litigation or Alternative Dispute Resolution, inter-group relations, and the like have increased dramatically in recent years. Of all significances of Alternative Dispute Resolution in conflict resolution and its impact on nation-building has received the least attention in peace and conflict studies. Consequently, not many empirical studies have been carried out to establish the nexus between Alternative Dispute Resolution and the modern-day conflict resolution in nation-building, thus creating a gap in knowledge. It is on this basis that this study is designed to systematically interrogate the significance of Alternative Dispute Resolution in conflict resolution and nation-building, focusing on its influence in achieving reconciliation and peace in Nigeria federation.

Importance of Communication in the Effectiveness of Alternative Dispute Resolution

Communication is the process of obtaining information or expressing thought and feelings (The Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, 1995 cited in Ogunsanya, 2017). According to Shannon and Weaver (1948 referenced in Gaber, 2022), communication is the procedures by which one mind may affect another. In line with the above definitions, it is clear that humans are inherently communicative; communication can occur in oral and written media as well as in music, visual arts, theatre, and all human behaviour; and communication is a process that entails sending a message from a sender to a recipient with the intention of eliciting a reaction or reactions (feedback). Communication encompasses all of the ways in which the parties interact with one another, including body language, spoken words, and tone of voice. Communication is significant because the way a message is conveyed is just as essential as its content. Communication in ADR involves providing factual information about the conflict situation, being able to discuss the parties' thoughts and worries, and touching on their views, interests, needs, and fears. Communication has emerged as a crucial conflict resolution tactic. Using communication skills, the third-party neutral attempts to persuade the disputants to come to a peaceful conclusion. Information sharing and exchange can be very beneficial in resolving conflicts, fostering mutual trust, and bringing about peace. However, poor communication can easily escalate conflicts between the warring parties. In order for the ADR centres to accomplish its central objective, the third-party neutral must be able to communicate effectively with his target audience or clients.

Effective communication is a significant element of the majority of non-violent conflict management techniques which include but not limited to cooperation, negotiation, discourse, as well as third-party interventions like mediation, conciliation, arbitration, etc, (Shedrack (2004). As a result, communication becomes a key component of peace and an efficient, non-adversarial method of resolution of disputes. Information is transmitted by means of a communication process which involves the exchange of facts, thoughts, value judgment and opinions. The channels of communication are selected based on the nature and purpose of the information, the speed required and above all, the requirements of the user (Laudon and Laudon, 2003). However, oral information flow tends to be the commonest form of transmitting information. Written word has significant advantages over the oral communication in the sense that written words provide a record of

message and improve receiver's rate of retention. Hence, information gathered by the ADR centre can be managed effectively when it is in the written form. Complaints come mostly in the written form, which will be documented and kept together; and this helps in the analysis and evaluation of such complaints towards achieving an amicable resolution.

It is important to note that in ADR centre, while the resolution process is taking place between the disputants, the third-party neutral facilitates dialogue. ADR centre shows sensitivity for the complainants' situation by the way it handles complaint which are usually forwarded in writing to the centre or walk to the centre to lodge the complaint (Adedeji, 2021b). In attempting to seek reconciliation and peace for parties in conflict, letter of invitation is sent to the respondent wherewith a complaint is lodged against. However, the respondent has the obligation to reply in writing. After the invitation, letter is expected to be received for the date and time of the meeting. Utmost important is the client's presence to the centre whenever they are invited for a tripartite meeting (case conference). It is important also that the parties must be willing to settle for peace. Since the foremost option of the process is resolution, the third-party neutral is expected to reproduce the stand of both parties and attract their attention and co-operation to an amicable resolution.

Research Methodology

The descriptive research design was adopted due to the nature of the study. Survey research design was chosen as types of resign design due to its constant record of proper selection of representative samples from the population and unbiased data collection in a very large target group that is spread across a large geographical area like the High Court of Lagos, Ikeja, Citizens' Mediation Bureau, Lagos and the Lagos Multi-Door Courthouse chosen as case studies. The study adopted quantitative method of research to carry out its task. Primary and secondary sources of data were used in the collection of data. The secondary source involves government document, publications of renowned scholars, conference reports, etc. Due to its survey design nature as primary source of data collection, the study employed the use of questionnaire with a view to obtain adequate information from the respondents.

The population of the study is Lagos State Ministry of Justice while the sampling size is High Court of Lagos, Ikeja, Citizens' Mediation Bureau and Lagos Multi-Door Courthouse, Lagos. A probability sampling technique using simple random sampling technique was adopted to ensure that every individual of the sampling size (staff and their clients) has equal privilege of being selected for the study. The involvement of the clients was to vary the characteristics of the sample population and get a balance outcome as much as possible. A total number of two hundred (200) questionnaires were administered randomly to individuals of the three selected government establishments equally. Inferential Statistics version of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and content analysis were used to analyse the primary and the secondary data respectively.

Analysis of the Result

This section presents the analysis of data collected through the administration of questionnaires. A total number of two hundred (200) questionnaires were distributed to individuals of selected establishments.

Table 1: Allocation of Questionnaires

Institutions	Allocation	Returned	%	Not Returned	%
High Court of Lagos, Ikeja	70	56	28	14	7
Citizens' Mediation Bureau	65	53	26.5	12	6
Lagos Multi-Door Courthouse, Lagos	65	51	25.5	14	7
Total	200	160	80	40	20

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

In line with the table 1, 80% of the questionnaires were filled and returned while 20% were not returned. Hence, the analysis was based on the one hundred and sixty (160) returned questionnaires.

Distribution of Responses According to Bio-Data Information

This subdivision focuses on the presentation of information of the selected respondents such as sex, marital status, age, academic qualification and employment levels.

Table 2: Bio-Data Information of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	100	62.5
	Female	60	37.5
	Total	160	100
Age Group	18–30	24	15.0
	31–40	56	35.0
	41–50	58	36.2
	51 & above	22	13.7
	Total	160	100
Marital Status	Single	50	31.2
	Married	106	66.2
	Divorced	4	2.5
	Total	160	100
Academic Qualification	Postgraduate	31	19.4
	Graduate	91	56.9
	ND	22	13.7
	O' Level	16	10.0
	Total	160	100
Employment Status	Civil Servant	70	43.7
	Business	64	40.0
	Student	26	16.2
	Total	160	100

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

On bio-data information of the respondents, table 2 showed that 62.5% of the respondents were male while 37.5% were female. The table similarly revealed that 15% of the respondents were between age brackets 18-30, 35% fall within 31-40, 36.2% were under the age bracket 41-50, while 13.7% fall within age bracket 51 and above. The breakdown of marital status showed that 31.2% were single, 66.2% were married while 2.5% were divorced. As also depicted above, 19.4% of the respondents were postgraduate, 56.9% were graduate, 13.7%, had National Diploma while

10% had O' Level Certificate. In addition, 43.7% of the respondent were Civil servants, 40% were in businesses related occupation while 16.2% were students.

Presentation of Data According to Variables

This section is to accomplish the task of the study, with the aim of interrogating the significance of Alternative Dispute Resolution in conflict resolution and nation-building focusing on its influence in achieving reconciliation and peace in Nigeria. The result of the inquiry is conveyed below, as the study adopted five (5) points Likert scales of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D) and Neutral (N) to analyse table 3.

Table 3: the Significance of Alternative Dispute Resolution in Conflict Resolution and Nation-Building

S/N	STATEMENTS	S/A	A	S/D	D	N
1.	The role played by Alternative Dispute Resolution is enough to ensure reconciliation and peace in Nigeria	26.2	60	0	2.5	11.2
2.	Good communication skill is apt in resolutions of disputes through the instrument of ADR	66.2	32.5	0	0	1.2
3.	Alternative Dispute Resolution is a cost-effective peaceful resolution mechanism	80	15	2.8	2.2	0
4.	Social justice is achieved when Alternative Dispute Resolution is employed in conflict resolution	57.5	22.5	10	8.7	1.2
5.	Alternative Dispute Resolution efforts have helped to decongest the courts in Nigeria	78.7	17.5	1.5	1.1	1.2
6.	Alternative Dispute Resolution creates an atmosphere of win-win solution for disputants	45	50	0	1.2	3.8
7.	Alternative Dispute Resolution has created a veritable platform for amicable settlement of disputes in Nigeria	35	51.2	4	1.2	8.6
8.	Members of the public are encouraged to utilise ADR as a means to resolve their disputes	33.8	61.2	1.3	1.2	2.5

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

It can be deduced from the table 3 that 26.2% and 60% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that the role played by ADR is enough to ensure reconciliation and peace in Nigeria, 2.5% disagreed and 11.2% were neutral. Equally, the table revealed that 98.7% of the respondents affirmed that good communication skill is apt in the resolutions of disputes through the instrument of ADR while 1.2% of respondents were ambivalent. Further, table 3 disclosed that 80% of the respondents strongly agreed that ADR is a cost-effective peaceful resolution mechanism, 15% agreed, while 2.8%, 2.2% and 2.5% respectively strongly disagreed, disagreed and neutral to the statement. The table as well showed that 57.5% and 22.5% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that social justice is achieved when Alternative Dispute Resolution is employed in conflict resolution, while 10%, 8.7% and 1.2% were strongly disagreed, disagreed and nonaligned respectively.

Table 3 also indicated that 78.7% and 17.5% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that Alternative Dispute Resolution efforts have helped to decongest the courts in Nigeria. Nevertheless, 2.6% did not consent to the testimony while 1.2% did not take sides. In line with the table 3, 95% of the respondents upheld the assertion that Alternative Dispute Resolution creates an atmosphere of win-win solution for the disputants, 1.2% disagreed, while and 3.8% played neutral. Similarly, it can be deduced from the table 3 that 35% and 51.2% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that Alternative Dispute Resolution has created a veritable platform for amicable settlement of disputes in Nigeria. On the other hand, 4% strongly disagreed, 1.2% disagreed with the statement as 8.6% were undecided. Table 3 further disclosed that 33.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 61.2% agreed, 1.3% strongly disagreed and 1.2% disagreed that members of the public are encouraged to utilise ADR as a means of resolving their disputes while 2.5% were indifferent.

Discussion of the Findings

The main aim of this study is to interrogate the significance of Alternative Dispute Resolution in conflict resolution and nation-building with specific focus on its impact in achieving reconciliation and peace in Nigeria. The findings of this study are derived from the earlier stated research objectives of the study. To get task of this section done, it is therefore required to restate the specific research objectives that guide this study which are: to analyse the impact of Alternative Dispute Resolution in achieving reconciliation and peace in contemporary Nigeria; and, to examine the relationship between Alternative Dispute Resolution and the modern-day conflict resolution in nation-building. The study found that ADR has positive impact on reconciliation and peace in the nation as 86.2% of the total respondents strongly affirmed the assertion that the role played by ADR is enough to ensure reconciliation and peace in Nigeria. This is supported by the literature as developing a mutual conciliatory between antagonistic persons or groups can only result to reconciliation (Kriesberg, 1998). Through ADR mechanism, harmony and co-operation between antagonists are reestablishing in a reciprocal manner (Fisher, 1999). ADR is proactive in creating an encounter where disputants share their perception experiences with one another which can mend their relationship. The implication of this is that ADR mechanisms which is win-win has been able to rewrite the old story of escalation of conflict through the instrument of court system which is win-lose approach.

Another positive impact deduced from the study is the reduction in the cost of getting justice through the application of ADR mechanism. 85% of the study respondents tolled the same line by robustly acknowledged that ADR is a cost-effective peaceful resolution mechanism as against diminutive fraction of 5% who opposed the assertion. According to Onyema (2013), one of the reasons for discontentment by the populace is prohibitive cost, which the emergence of ADR has redressed (Oluyede, 1994). The work has also proved that there is mutual relationship between ADR and the modern-day conflict resolution in nation-building. The study has found that application of ADR has help to decongest the courts across the nation. Osinbajo (2005) argued that the establishment of the Lagos multi-door courthouse (LMDC) in 2002 drastically reduced myriads of cases at the docket of Lagos high court. Backing the narrative is the stand of 96.2% of the respondents who absolutely agreed that ADR efforts have helped to decongest the courts in Nigeria. Creating a veritable platform for amicable settlement of disputes in Nigeria will help the nation to live a peaceful life where developments can be sustained. The study has discovered that ADR has created such veritable platform for amicable settlement of disputes in Nigeria as it was recorded in the analysis that 86.2% of the total respondents corroborated the testimonial. Supporting this finding is Oluyede (1994) who established that ADR provides a friendly resolution of conflict for people at free of charge or at a reduced rate. In evaluating the instrument, the study

found that ADR allows for informality as its rules of procedure are flexible; application of equity rather than the rule of law; it is a cost and time effective approach of conflict resolution; it builds communication and the opportunity for reconciliation between disputants; and increases the satisfaction of disputants through its win-win solution as few identified advantages over litigation (Goldberg et al, 1992; Ekpenyong, 2014; and Aina, 2005).

Despite these remarkable identified strengths of ADR over litigation, the study also identified few flaws in the mechanism such as lack of precedent, inappropriate in the context of extreme power imbalance between parties, lack of uniformity of operational policy, not appropriate for cases of public sanction or punishment, and paucity of expert coupled with inadequate training among the practitioners (Adedeji, 2021c). Overwhelmingly, the model of ADR is a result-oriented strategy in conflict resolution with wide influence on nation-building. The study acknowledged its capability to contribute to nation-building. In line with the above statistical analysis, the model ensures reconciliation and peace, reestablishment of harmony and co-operation between antagonists, reduction in the cost of getting justice and decongestion of courts across the nation. Other roles played by ADR are the provision of friendly resolution of conflict at free of charge or at a reduced rate, time effective approach of conflict resolution and increases the satisfaction of ADR win-win outcome by disputants. Connivingly, ADR has created a veritable platform for amicable settlement of disputes in Nigeria, and this has helped stability of the nation, and hence peaceful atmosphere where developments are sustained.

Conclusion

An attempt has been made to discuss the significance of Alternative Dispute Resolution model in conflict resolution and nation-building with the special focus on its influence on reconciliation and peace in Nigeria. According to the study, peaceful resolution of disputes can foster the conditions necessary for conducting public affairs in a peaceful manner, which will in turn aid in the development of a nation. Alternative Dispute Resolution has a clear mandate to promote reconciliation and peace in Nigeria and beyond. It is ideally positioned to serve as a springboard for the amicable resolution of disputes due to its unique advantage over the judicial instruments. Further, ADR model institution has different approaches and perspective to the matter of conflict resolution. In contrast to the court, Alternative Dispute Resolution requires moral equity in its operations, which expands and restricts the process of litigation and interprets them not in accordance with precise letter of law but rather in accordance with the spirit of justice, fairness, and reason. As submitted by the study, ADR has a reciprocal link with peace and reconciliation.

Recommendation

The significance of Alternative Dispute Resolution in conflict resolution and nation-building most perhaps acknowledged, thus from the facts analysed, the study makes certain recommendations thus:

1. A thorough public awareness initiative should be mounted on radio, television and the newspapers as well as public enlightenment to the consciousness of the vast majority of Lagos and Nigerian population not only about the influence, but also about gaining access to the centre and the methods adopted by the centre to resolve conflict.
2. It is recommended that Lagos Multi-Door Courthouse as a matter of necessity embark on decentralisation policy by establishing more LMDC centre across Lagos State to cater for

the teeming population seeking for justice. This will bring access to justice closer to people of Lagos through activities and presence of the LMDC.

3. Due to the importance of communication for the functioning of people and organisation, information's must be planned and organised so as to avoid distortions. To aid this, both public and private ADR centres should move with the trend and dynamics of technology for improvement in their efficiency. Appropriate internet facilities should be adopted for free flow of information.
4. The need for ADR acts in Nigeria is key for the sake of uniformity of practice by various practitioners. Operational policy should be formulated by the government of Nigeria to serve as the baseline of ADR uniqueness across the country. This will encourage the standardisation of the model.
5. Both public and private Alternative Dispute Resolution centres should be staffed by skilled and well-trained professionals who can manage the many individuals that visit ADR centres on a daily basis in search of redress. To complement this, the Centres should organise constant training and seminar/conference to meet up with the global best ADR practices.

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